

What We Study: Knowledge Networks in Higher Education Policymaking

This research project, *Transnational Knowledge Networks in Higher Education Policymaking*, funded by the Academy of Finland, studies knowledge networks and their operation and influence in the field of higher education policy.

The Principal Investigator of the project is Professor Jaakko Kauko (jaakko.kauko@tuni.fi, +358 50 318 7788). The researchers working in the project are Katri Eeva, Jarmo Kallunki, Paula Saarinen, and Joni Forsell. The research group is supported by an international advisory board and temporary research assistants. The project is hosted by Tampere University Faculty of Education and Culture.

Your Rights as a Research Participant

Based on your work and position in your organisation, we have identified you as a key network actor in the higher education policy field, and we would therefore like to invite you to participate in our research. Participation is voluntary. Participation in this case means you agree to be interviewed. We obtained your contact details from your organisation's internet pages.

The project's researchers are committed to good scientific practice and the Ethical Principlesⁱ of the Finnish National Board of Research Integrity. The research will be reported to ensure the **research participants cannot generally be recognised**. The other participants may occasionally recognise a pseudonymised participant in cases where several participants have been present in a situation (e.g. multiple interviewees) or in cases where another person working in the same organisation knows its work very well. If the participant is willing, the research can be reported more openly, provided that this does not compromise other participants' anonymity.

A participant has the right to stop the interview without giving any reason and without consequences. A participant has the right to check the transcribed version of their own interviews.

Detailed Information

The Objectives of the Research

The main objective of the *Transnational Knowledge Networks in Higher Education Policymaking* research project is to study **how Finnish higher education policymaking operates in the European framework**. We map the role of transnational knowledge networks, analyse the flow and selection of knowledge in these networks, and study the soft power they produce. The research combines network analysis, interviews, and observations. The network analysis maps the actors working in and between Finland and the EU and their relations, and the aim is to map and understand the creation, selection, and uses of knowledge in this network through interviews and observations, as well as the transformation of knowledge as it passes through the network.

The Implementation of the Research

The project runs from September 2021 until August 2025. The archival and documentary materials for the network analysis has been mainly collected in 2021 and 2022. Interview and observational data will be mainly collected in 2022 and 2023. The publication phase is expected to start in 2023.

The network analysis is based on public materials, and it does not require the participant's time or consent. Participation in the observations requires the participant's consent but not time. Participation in interviews also requires the participant's time, and depending on the interview it will take about an hour.

There are no financial rewards for the research participants.

Benefits and Risks for the Research Participant

There are no immediate gains for the participant. The results are basic research on a topic that has not been widely studied. They may help build new understanding about how knowledge is used in policymaking, and the role the use of knowledge plays in the relationships between Finland and the EU.

There are no health or economic risks related to our research methods. Social and political risks are related to the possibility of a participant being

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recognised. The research results are reported to ensure the research participants cannot generally be recognised (e.g. by using generic terms such as 'official', 'public servant', 'politician', or 'researcher'). Despite even the best efforts to protect anonymity, there is a risk of a participant being recognised when reporting situations in which multiple participants have been present (for example, in observed meetings only a limited number of people are typically present). Risks pertaining to the handling of personal data are controlled by careful data management (see below).

Privacy, Confidentiality, Data Management, and Data Storage

The data collected from the research participants are handled confidentially according to the EU's general data protection regulations (GDPR) and Finnish data protection laws. For a detailed description see the attached Privacy Notice, which is also available on the project's websiteⁱⁱ and in the Tampere University document archives.

Data collected in this project are stored and handled in Tampere University's password-protected secure network drive. Access to the drive is restricted to the member of the research group and research assistants. Data are not handled in cloud services, but pseudonymised versions of data may be analysed for publication purposes in services that are compatible with the GDPR regulations (e.g. Microsoft OneDrive). Data is only transferred through secure channels (VPN or encrypted portable devices). See the Data Management Plan for more information.

During the data collection, manual data are minimised, and they are digitised as soon as possible. After digitisation, handwritten memos are destroyed.

The network data may be combined with the interview and observational data. The network analysis is used to study links through which the knowledge is transmitted.

The research data are in principle only accessible to the research group's members. Data are not shared outside the research group, with the following exceptions: the co-authors of publications (e.g. advisory board members) may access pseudonymised data extracts or information gathered from public sources. Students may access pseudonymised data under the supervision of the research group members for their thesis work

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after a case-by-case risk evaluation. No data is left permanently in outsiders' possession.

Data collected from public sources for the network analysis are stored permanently in the Finnish Social Science Archives (FSD). Regarding the other data, only the names of the observed groups and interviewees can be published: if the participant wishes, or the researchers consider publishing risky for the participant, this information can also be withheld from publication.

Depending on the data's sensitivity, an agreement with the participant can be made so that the data are more openly accessible to outsiders. In this case, it can be agreed to store the interview in the FSD and opened to other researchers after an embargo (e.g. 5–20 years).

When it has not been agreed to store interview and observational data in the FSD, they will be stored by Tampere University for follow-up studies until 2040, after which they will be destroyed.

Funding

This project is funded by the Academy of Finland (grant number: 340267).

Voluntary Participation

Participation in the research is fully voluntary, and you can stop your participation at any time. You can also temporarily suspend your participation. **If you decide to cease your participation, the researchers can use the data collected until that point.**

During the project you have the right to check the transcribed version of your own interview(s). A request to check the transcription should be presented in the interview situation or shortly after it, in which case the transcription will be provided for checking as soon as it has been prepared.

Privacy in Research Publications and Reporting of Results

The research publications focus on the research project's main theoretical goals, and the focus is on knowledge networks and their operation. References to the interviews and observations are made so that individuals cannot generally be recognised. The potential risk of recognition is described above.

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A summary of the final research results and/or research articles will be sent by email to the interviewees and chairpersons of the observed groups. The results will be reported in peer-reviewed scientific journals and book chapters. The researchers will be available for various events to give talks and discuss the research project's findings.

Continued Use of the Research Materials

The data collected in this project are not used for any other purpose than scientific research. Data can be used for continued research and publications following the protocols mentioned above.

For More Information

Any further enquiries about the research project can be addressed either to the present researcher or the Principal Investigator.

- Principal Investigator, Professor Jaakko Kauko (jaakko.kauko@tuni.fi, +358 50 318 7788)
- Postdoctoral researcher Katri Eeva (katri.eeva@tuni.fi, +358 50 407 5248)
- Researcher Jarmo Kallunki (jarmo.kallunki@tuni.fi, +358 50 318 2277).

Attachments

Annex 1. Data Management Plan.

Annex 2. Privacy Notice.

Annex 3. Participation Form.

ⁱ TENK (3/2019). The ethical principles of research with human participants and ethical review in the human sciences in Finland.

https://tenk.fi/sites/default/files/2021-01/Ethical_review_in_human_sciences_2020.pdf

ⁱⁱ <https://research.tuni.fi/eduknow/knets/>

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